

Mechanical Properties of 2 D Carbon-Carbon Composites Produced from Thermosetting Resin Precursors.

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Abstract

The production of carbon fibre reinforced carbon composites has evolved into an inefficient, multistep batch process. The reason for this being the low carbon yields obtained from the precursor resins. Several reimpregnation/carbonization stages are required to increase the composites' density and thus improve properties. Their microstructure is dominated by large scale, irregular shaped porosity, and shrinkage cracks produced as a consequence of the method of fabrication. The complex mechanical properties of 2-dimensional (fabric reinforced) carbon-carbon, produced by this method have been measured both after the initial carbonization and following multiple densification cycles. The efficiency of the densification process is discussed, with particular emphasis on the interlaminar response. Material of this type, with its brittle matrix phases, is particularly vulnerable to interlaminar fracture. This mode of failure has been studied by the application of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics.

1. Introduction

Carbon-carbon composites are a specialised family of carbon fibre reinforced composite materials. They are similar to carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites save that in this case both fibres and matrix are carbon. The materials are produced in order to combine the advantages of fibre reinforced composites (high specific strength, stiffness and in-plane toughness) with the refractory properties of engineering ceramics (1). Carbon-carbon materials are used in the heat shields of re-entry vehicles, brakes and clutches on aircraft, racing cars, high speed trains and Main Battle Tanks, and in rocket motors. Furthermore, their chemical inertness and biocompatibility has attracted interest in biomechanical engineering.

A number of fabrication technologies, capable of filling the interstices between the fibres, are available including chemical vapour deposition, pyrolysis of thermosetting resins and high

pressure carbonization of pitches (2). Composites can be made in a wide variety of forms, from unidirectional tows, tapes, felts or woven fabrics and three dimensional preforms (3). Fibre orientation variations result in diverse mechanical and other properties. Any of the different types of carbon fibre may be used as reinforcement from "low" modulus rayon based fibres to "ultra-high" modulus fibres made from mesophase pitch precursors (4). A further level of complexity arises in the production of carbon-carbon composites, that of variation in the structure of the matrix. The carbon matrix may consist of a glassy isotropic carbon through to a highly crystalline graphite with almost limitless variations and combinations in between. It is prudent therefore to consider carbon-carbon not as a single entity, but rather as a whole family of materials whose structure and properties may be tailored to suit a large number of specialist applications (1).

2. Thermosetting resin matrix precursors.

Thermosetting resins are attractive matrix precursors because they are relatively easy materials with which to impregnate fibres and because a large technology data base exists from their use in the "conventional" composites industry. All of the methods proved in this field such as filament winding, autoclave cured prepreg, hand lay up or pultrusion, may be employed to produce large artifacts of complex geometry. The most important attribute of a carbon matrix precursor is a high carbon yield, ie. a low weight loss during carbonization. The number of compounds that could be considered candidates for liquid phase impregnants is almost limitless. When all of the processing and property requirements are reviewed, however, the choice is constrained to very few materials. Only a handful of resins possess carbon yields of at least 40% after pyrolysis. The choice is generally limited to phenolic and furan systems. A great deal of research has been carried out investigating high carbon-yield resins based on polyimides, polyphenylene and acetylene terminated aromatics (1). The work on commercialising high yield systems has proved unsuccessful to date. There are basically three reasons for this. These highly aromatic polymers have proved extremely difficult to process, when pyrolysed the resins have tended to form "closed-pore" structures preventing further densification and finally, excessive raw materials cost. Some of the systems examined have been so expensive that they would have been more suitable as a form of currency than as engineering materials!

Thermoset resins form a glassy isotropic carbon upon pyrolysis in an inert atmosphere (5), which does not graphitize even at temperatures up to 3000°C. The carbon yields obtained from suitable thermoset precursors usually vary between 50 and 65% (6). The low density of the carbon formed ($\approx 1.5 \text{gcm}^{-3}$) may preclude its use in certain applications, but there are many others in which a strong non-graphitic matrix is desirable. There is one exception to the normal behaviour in carbon-carbon densification. Shrinkage stresses in the vicinity of the fibre can cause the isotropic matrix to graphitise at high temperatures (7,8).

Relatively little initial capital investment in equipment is required to operate the thermoset resin fabrication route compared

to its competitors. The techniques perfected in the polymer composites industry may be successfully transferred and modified to allow the production of large complex structures. The technique is however labour intensive, especially in the production of laminated structures, and requires a good degree of operator skill and experience. Following the curing there is a post cure cycle in order to finish chemical crosslinking and expel any remaining volatiles. The composite is subsequently carbonized in an inert atmosphere at around 850 - 1000°C. The low carbon yields obtained necessitates an inefficient batch process involving multiple reimpregnation/carbonization cycles to increase density and thus improve properties. 4 or more densification cycles will generally be required before the component is considered complete. Heat treatment to graphitization temperatures in excess of 2500°C shrinks the matrix increasing the degree of open porosity and aiding further densification. Even if a fully graphitised product is not required, the initial stages of the multiple step process often involve one or more graphitization treatments in order to attain an acceptable density more quickly.

3. Experimental procedure.

3.1 Sample preparation

The basic precursor material was a woven fabric reinforced phenolic resin prepreg produced by a solvent process (1). The fibres were "standard modulus" Hercules AS4, woven into a 280 gm², 8-harness satin fabric. The resin matrix precursor used was Borden Chemicals' SC1008. Prepreg was produced to contain 50% ±2% by weight of resin. Flat laminates, 10 plies thick, were fabricated by a vacuum bag autoclave cure. Once cured the laminates, approximately 3mm thick, were post cured to remove any residual water from the condensation curing reaction. The composites were converted to carbon-carbon by heating to 1000°C in an inert atmosphere, at a heating rate of 1°C min⁻¹.

The carbon-carbon laminates were divided into two groups one of which was evaluated straight away, the other densified prior to testing. The densification process followed a procedure typical of that which would be used commercially. The laminates were graphitised by heating to 2500°C and subsequently vacuum impregnated with 50:50 mixture of furan resin (Quaker Oats Qua- Corr No 1001) and Pitch (Ashland A240). The reimpregnated samples were carbonized to 1000°C followed by a further graphitization treatment. A total of 5 densification cycles were used, the bulk density of the material being recorded after each.

Before testing could be carried out it was necessary to produce samples of the appropriate geometry. Despite their apparent toughness carbon-carbon composites are extremely susceptible to damage during machining. In order to avoid fraying and disorientation during preparation, the laminates were secured to a backing plate of acrylic sheet using double sided sticky tape prior to slitting using a water lubricated diamond saw. All testing was carried out using an Instron model 4505 servomechanical test frame fitted with a 10KN load cell. The machine was operated in "position control" at a constant displacement of 1mm.min⁻¹. The use of a

servomechanical test frame is recommended over its servohydraulic competitors because it is inherently more accurate in position control, which is vital when dealing with such low strain materials as this.

3.2 Density measurements

The density of a carbon-carbon composite is generally used as a qualitative measure of the mechanical properties, efficiency of production and in quality control. The complex structure of the material with its various phases, open and closed porosity necessitates the use of a number of techniques for a complete characterisation. Having said that, the bulk density is normally sufficient for most purposes. The volume of the specimens may be found using a water displacement technique unless they contain an appreciable percentage of open porosity. Under these conditions water will enter the pores and produce an artificially high value of density. In these circumstances it is advisable to accurately machine a sample of the material into a geometry whose volume can be easily calculated, a cube for example. The bulk density was calculated from:

$$\rho = m/v \quad (1).$$

where ρ is the density, m the mass and v the volume.

3.3 Flexure testing.

In the development of carbon-carbon systems relatively simple tests are the most appropriate. Consequently the majority of strength and modulus measurements are carried out using the three point flexure test (Figure 1). The ultimate flexure strength (σ_f) and the flexure modulus (E_f) were calculated as follows:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3Pl}{2bd^2} \quad (2).$$

$$E_f = \frac{l^3m}{4bd^3} \quad (3).$$

Where the symbols represent the specimen dimensions in Figure 1, and m is the slope of the linear portion of the load-deflection curve. Flexure testing imposes tension, compression and a degree of shear loading on the sample simultaneously and thus cannot provide data suitable for design purposes. It is however valuable in performing comparisons between materials or to determine the effects of different processing and environmental conditions etc. Shear deflections can seriously reduce the apparent modulus of highly anisotropic composites. A span/depth ratio of 40/1 was used to avoid this problem.

3.4 Interlaminar shear strength.

Carbon-carbon, especially that made by the resin pyrolysis route in the 1- or 2-D form, is particularly prone to interlaminar failure. One test frequently quoted in the literature is the short beam interlaminar shear strength (ASTM D2344) (9). A shortened span on a three-point flexural test fixture, with a span to depth ratio of 4:1, is used in order to maximise the shear stress at the neutral axis. Testing was performed as shown in Figure 2. The short beam shear strength (ILS) was calculated as follows:

$$ILS = \frac{3P}{4bd} \quad (4).$$

where P is the failure load, b the width of specimen and d the thickness. For the result to be meaningful, the failure mode must be either single or multiple shear. The test is extremely useful in comparing materials. It should be remembered though that flaws and defects in the specimens would generally disqualify them from the test (10). Since carbon-carbon composites usually contain a large number of different types of flaws the validity of the results will always be somewhat questionable.

3.5 Plane strain fracture toughness

The toughness of a material is best described as its ability to resist crack propagation from a pre-existing flaw. Determination of the fracture toughness parameters of carbon-carbon ought then to be a priority since flaws of one form or another are in abundance. The stress intensity factor K_{IC} describes the state of stress in the vicinity of a crack as a function of the specimen geometry, the crack geometry and the applied load in mode I fracture. The K_{IC} of the carbon-carbon was evaluated in the Single Edge-Notched Beam configuration, a test "borrowed" from monolithic ceramics testing (Figure 3)(11). The crack was formed using a slow speed diamond wire saw to a depth of $d/2$. K_{IC} was calculated from:

$$K_{IC} = \left(\frac{Pl}{bd^{3/2}} \right) y \quad (5).$$

Where P is the load at failure, l the span, b the specimen breadth, a the initial crack length and y is a geometrical factor dependent on specimen geometry and (a/d) ratio (12,13).

3.6 Interlaminar fracture toughness

All materials contain flaws which release energy when they propagate under load (14). The critical strain energy release rate (G_{IC}), during delamination by stable crack growth, was investigated using a double cantilever beam (DCB) test (Figure 4)(15). According to simple beam theory, a crack extension from a to (a+ Δa) induces a change in compliance resulting in a loss of strain energy dU. The mode I strain energy release rate is defined as:

$$G_{IC} = -\frac{1}{b} \frac{dU}{da} \quad (6).$$

where U is the total energy stored in the specimen and b its width.

Consider now a typical load/displacement/crack-length curve for an interlaminar crack propagating in a composite (Figure 5), where F and δ are the applied load and resulting deflection. The DCB specimen is loaded to F_i whence the crack begins to extend. The load will drop to F_{i+1} while the crack extends from a_i to $(a_i + \Delta a_{i+1})$. The loss in strain energy due to the extension of the crack is the area ΔA . In a brittle material, provided the increment between δ_i and δ_{i+1} is sufficiently small for the load deflection curve to approximate to a straight line, then:

$$-dU = dA = \frac{1}{2}(F_i \delta_{i+1} - F_{i+1} \delta_i) \quad (7).$$

A mean value of G_{IC} may be determined by measuring F_i , F_{i+1} , δ_i and δ_{i+1} for a series of n crack extensions of length $(a_{i+1} - a_i)$.

$$G_{IC} = \frac{1}{2b \sum_{i=1}^n (a_{i+1} - a_i)} \times \sum_{i=1}^n (F_i \delta_{i+1} - F_{i+1} \delta_i) \quad (8)$$

In carrying out DCB tests on carbon-carbon it was found that simply attaching hinges to the surface of the laminates often resulted in flexural failure of the two half beams rather than inter laminar crack propagation. The problem was rectified by bonding a 16 ply UD carbon fibre reinforced polymer composite to both sides of the carbon-carbon prior to attaching the loading hinges. This served to restrict the flexural deformation in the beams and cause cracks to propagate along the beams in the required manner. The specimens were 150mm in length and 25mm wide. Interlaminar starter cracks 50mm in length were produced using a diamond wire saw. Crack length measurement was achieved via resistive crack gauges affixed to one side of the test specimen. The signals from the test machine and crack length measuring apparatus were interfaced with a computer programmed to calculate G_{IC} using equation 8. Values of G_{IC} were calculated from the gradients of the best-fit lines to the plots of incremental energy (ΔU_i) versus incremental crack area ($2b(a_{i+1} - a_i)$).

4. Results and discussion

The microstructure of the composites following carbonization was dominated by large scale porosity and shrinkage cracks. The porosity resulted from the volatilization of small molecules and heteroatoms during pyrolysis. The matrix can shrink by up to 50% during carbonization whilst the fibres' geometry remains unchanged. Porosity and micro-cracks are thus an inevitable consequence of the production route (Figure 6). Heat treatment to 2500°C results in further shrinkage of the carbon matrix as it gradually transforms into a graphitic structure. The value of intermediate graphitization cycles thus becomes obvious since they improve the efficiency of subsequent impregnation and re-carbonization processes by increased access to porosity. Figure 7 shows a polarized light micrograph of the densified composite. Reimpregnation, even after five iterations, has failed to fully densify the composite as may be inferred from the observations that the reimpregnant carbon tends to line the pores and cracks rather than fill them in.

Figure 8 demonstrates how the density of the composite increased rapidly with the first two or three reimpregnation cycles but then reached a plateau such that there is little to be gained from carrying out more than four or five cycles. The redensification process appears to follow a " $\frac{1}{2}$ power law". This "law of diminishing returns" arises because some of the surface pores become blocked after the first few cycles, thus reducing the efficiency of subsequent treatments. Despite the fact that liquid reimpregnants are often considerably "thinned down" using solvents, it is extremely difficult to densify areas in the centre of thick components. The blocking effect of the densified outer plies is

such that it is difficult to improve on the density beyond 1.8gcm^3 . The inability of the multiple impregnation cycles to fill/heal the porosity and shrinkage cracks formed during carbonization results in a relatively large number of cracks and voids present in the microstructure of fully dense composites (Figure 7). Optical anisotropy can be discerned indicating the presence of graphitic carbon in the matrix. The graphitic carbon is observed to be grading continuously into an isotropic matrix as the distance from the fibres increases. One may thus conclude that the microstructure of the matrix produced from thermosetting precursors is strongly affected by the presence of fibres and the associated thermal stresses at the interfaces.

The mechanical test results in Table 1 illustrate the effectiveness of the densification process. The modulus, flexural strength and interlaminar shear strengths are increased by approximately a factor of three in line with a density increase from 1.42gcm^3 to 1.78gcm^3 . In addition to improving both strength and modulus, the graphitization and redensification processes were observed to change the nature of the material's fracture behaviour. A transition from a brittle failure mode towards a more pseudo-plastic fracture was recorded with a corresponding increase in failure strain (Figure 9). The two types of composite tested exhibited what are, for essentially ceramic materials, remarkably high values of plane strain fracture toughness (K_{IC}) (Table 1). Such results are unfortunately invalid. Crack propagation was interrupted and deflected by the fibres such that the principles of linear elastic fracture mechanics are not applicable (Figure 10). When crack propagation occurs collinear with the initial crack, as was the case in the DCB test, valid fracture toughness parameters can be evaluated.

The interlaminar fracture toughness of the carbonized sample was found to be of the order of 110Jm^2 whilst that measured for the fully densified samples was 130Jm^2 . These values are very low, around half that measured for even the most brittle epoxy composites, and an order of magnitude less than thermoplastic and toughened epoxy matrix composites (16). The extremely brittle nature of the matrix and the presence of voids and shrinkage cracks explains why components are sometimes observed to fail due to delamination during processing. The electron micrographs in Figure 11 show that composites formed by this production route offer very little resistance to the propagation of interlaminar cracks. Flaws introduced during the first pyrolysis cycle may grow as a result of the thermal loading of subsequent cycles such that the materials are extremely unpredictable. A 2-D composite may thus fail by delamination without warning during processing, machining or in service. The higher value of G_{IC} observed in the densified material is probably due to the filling of some of the cracks and pores by the reimpregnation. This would tend to reduce their stress concentrating effect. Having said that, the value measured is still very low and needs to be improved if these materials are to find further application.

5. Conclusion.

Carbon-carbon composites are an extremely multifarious and diverse

family of materials. Two dimensional woven composites produced from thermoset resin matrix precursors, for example, are formed by an inefficient multistage process. The basic composite may be densified by a variety of methods such that the finished product is a complex multiphase material. The degree of complexity is further enhanced by the heat treatment temperature (HTT). The matrix may vary from a "glassy", isotropic carbon through to a polycrystalline graphite with increasing HTT. Our present level of understanding of the various factors and interactions involved is such that only a qualitative explanation of the measured properties is possible. It is necessary to carry out a great deal of "detective work" in order to evaluate the material. A number of tests and microscopical examinations are required to build up a picture of what is actually happening.

The densification process is successful in that it affords a significant improvement in mechanical properties. On the other hand, even so-called "fully dense" material contains a significant proportion of cracks, voids and other inhomogeneities which limit its ultimate performance. The modified DCB test appears to be a very useful tool in characterising the delamination failure mode in a 2-D carbon-carbon. It has been able to emphasise a serious property defect which must be addressed in order to increase confidence in the composites' performance as engineering materials.

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Table 1. Mechanical properties of 2D carbon-carbon composites

Material	Bulk density (gcm⁻³)	Flexure strength (MNm⁻²)	Flexure modulus (GNm⁻²)	Failure strain (%)	Interlaminar shear strength (MNm⁻²)	Fracture toughness (K_{IC}) (MNm^{-3/2})	G_{IC} (Jm⁻²)
Carbonized (1 cycle)	1.42	70.34	65.3	0.11	4.2	7.6	110
Densified (multicycle)	1.78	220	160.7	0.14	12.2	8.1	130

P = load
 l = span
 b = breadth of specimen
 d = depth of specimen

Figure 1. The 3 point flexure test geometry.

Figure 2. Interlaminar shear test configuration (courtesy Instron Ltd.).

Figure 3. Single Edge-Notched Beam test geometry.

Figure 4. The DCB. test geometry.

Figure 5. Typical force-displacement-crack length curve recorded during the DCB test.

Figure 6. Optical micrograph of carbonized carbon-carbon composite.

Figure 7. Polarized light micrograph of densified carbon-carbon composite.

Figure 8. Effect of reimpregnation/carbonization cycles on the density of a 2D carbon-carbon composite.

Figure 9. Fracture behaviour of carbonized and fully-dense carbon-carbon composites.

Figure 10. Schematic representation of the failure mode observed during K_{IC} testing of 2D carbon-carbon.

Figure 11. Interlaminar fracture faces of a) carbonized and b) fully dense composites exhibit little resistance to crack propagation.